

Fatigue Life Prediction of Dissimilar Material Joints using Neural Networks

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Background of the Study

< Composite materials trends >

- Dissimilar material joints, which combine composite materials with metals, are widely used in aerospace and automotive industries due to their high specific strength, stiffness, and long fatigue life
- With the trend of replacing metal materials with composites, there is a growing need for research on composite-metal joints
- Since fatigue damage is one of the principal causes of joint failure, predicting the fatigue life of joints is essential

Research Objectives

Propose a neural network-based method to predict fatigue life of dissimilar material joints with improved accuracy and reduced computational cost

- Investigate fatigue behavior of bonded and hybrid joints with varying overlap lengths**
- Predict fatigue life using neural networks trained on experimental data**
- Bayesian regularized to prevent overfitting and enhance model generalization**
- Compare neural network predictions with experimental S-N curves for validation**

Specimen preparation & Experiment

<Specimen preparation >

- Composite specimens made by cutting unidirectional prepregs into 250 mm×250 mm
- Hand lay-up lamination $[0/90]_{5s}$, autoclave curing and machining
- Glass fiber reinforced plastic tabs, Specimen bonding surface treated with #400 silicon carbide paper and acetone degreasing, Tabs attached with EA9309.3NA adhesive
- SS400 steel specimens were prepared similarly, with a GFRP tab, acetone treatment, and Teroson EP 5016 adhesive bonding

Materials and Methods

Specimen preparation & Experiment

<Geometry of joint specimen
(a) Bonded joint (b) Hybrid joint >

<Geometry of joint specimen
(a) Bonded joint (b) Hybrid joint >

Tensile Test

- 6 tests per joint; average values used
- Universal Testing Machine at room temperature
- Displacement control: 0.2 mm/min
- Force–displacement curves obtained for reference

Fatigue Test

- Load levels selected from the elastic range of tensile results
- Bonded Joint: 65%, 60%, 57% of failure load
- Hybrid Joint: 60%, 55%, 50% of failure load (Hydraulic servo-type machine (SALT Co.))
- Load control, sinusoidal wave, 3 Hz frequency
- Tension–tension fatigue, $R = 0.1$, 6 tests per load level; F–N diagrams constructed

Materials and Methods

Bayesian Regularized Neural Network (BNN)

< Comparison of an artificial neural network (ANN) and a Bayesian Regularized Neural Network (BNN) >

Feature	Standard Neural Network (ANN)	Bayesian Regularized Neural Network (BRANN)
Goal	Minimize prediction error only	Minimize both prediction error and model complexity
Loss function	$E_D \rightarrow$ focuses only on data error	$\beta E_D + \alpha E_W \rightarrow$ balances error and weight size
Weight treatment	Single fixed optimal value	Treated as a probability distribution (uncertainty-aware)
Generalization	Higher risk of overfitting	Better generalization and robustness
Data requirement	Needs a large dataset to perform well	More stable with small or noisy datasets
Overfitting	Likely if regularization is weak	Actively avoids overfitting by penalizing complexity

Loss function

- In general, neural networks aim to minimize the sum of squared errors E_D

$$E_D = \sum_{i=1}^n (t_i - a_i)^2$$

- t_i : the target value of the training data
- a_i : the predicted value produced by the neural network

- However, to reduce model complexity and prevent overfitting, a regularization term E_W , which represents the sum of squared network weights, is added. The objective function becomes:

$$F = \beta E_D + \alpha E_W$$

- α : the weighting factor for the weight magnitude term
- β : the weighting factor for the data error term

Bayes' theorem

- **Without prior knowledge:**
Distribution narrows around 0.78 as more data are added, increasing confidence.
 - **With a prior following a Normal distribution 0.5:**
Estimate keeps a shape similar to the prior while progressively approaching the true value
- ➔ By applying such Bayesian prior probabilities to constrain the weights, this approach aims to prevent overfitting caused by excessively large weights

Bayesian regularization

$$P(\alpha, \beta | D, M) = \frac{P(D | \alpha, \beta, M) P(\alpha, \beta | M)}{P(D | M)}$$

- w : the weight vector (connection strengths) of the neural network
 - D : the training dataset
 - M : the neural network architecture (model)
 - α, β : hyperparameters used for regularization
1. $P(w | \alpha, M)$: the Gaussian prior distribution that encourages the weights to remain small
 2. $P(D | w, \beta, M)$: the likelihood, representing how well the data fit given the current weights
- ➔ This formulation means that as more data are observed, the posterior becomes narrower, while a strong prior keeps the estimate close to the prior beliefs
- ➔ In other words, it balances data fit and prior constraints to prevent excessively large weights (model complexity) and reduce overfitting

Materials and Methods

Flow chart for Bayesian optimization of regularization parameters

Error Term Calculation

- The objective function combines data error and weight decay error from training data.

Application of the Levenberg–Marquardt Algorithm

- The algorithm updates the weights in the direction that minimizes the objective function.

Effective Number of Parameters γ

- The Gauss–Newton approximation is used to compute the model complexity γ

Updating α and β

- Using the newly calculated γ , update the regularization parameters α and β .

Convergence Check

- YES** → Training complete → **Generalized BRANN model** is formed
- NO** → Repeat the above steps

Levenberg-Marquardt

- A hybrid between Gradient Descent and the Gauss–Newton method

Minimize $F = \beta E_D + \alpha E_W$

- **Weight Update Rule:** $w_{new} = w_{old} - (J^T J + \lambda I)^{-1} J^T e$
- J : Jacobian matrix (partial derivatives of the error function with respect to weights)
- e : Error vector (e.g., $e = y - f(x, w)$)
- λ : Damping factor (adjusts between gradient descent and Gauss–Newton behavior)

If λ is large \rightarrow behaves like gradient descent (slow but stable)

If λ is small \rightarrow behaves like Gauss–Newton (faster but potentially unstable)

Gauss–Newton Approximation & Parameter Update

This is the stage where the model complexity (γ) is estimated, and the regularization parameters (α and β) are updated accordingly

- Estimating the Effective Number of Parameters (γ)
- γ quantifies how complex the model is
- The computed value of γ is used in the regularization parameter update step:

$$\gamma = n - 2\alpha^{MAP} \text{tr}(H^{MAP})^{-1}$$

- n : Total number of parameters
- $(H^{MAP})^{-1}$: Approximate inverse Hessian matrix at the MAP estimate

$$\alpha^{new} = \frac{\gamma}{2E_w(w^{new})}$$

$$\beta^{new} = \frac{n - \gamma}{2E_D(w^{new})}$$

BRANN-Based Fatigue Life Prediction

Levenberg–Marquardt Algorithm

- Minimizes the objective function:

$$F = \beta E_D + \alpha E_W$$

- Efficiently finds weights that balance accuracy and smoothness
- Enables fast convergence and stable learning even with small datasets

BRANN uses this algorithm to update weights while preserving generalization

Gauss–Newton Approximation & Parameter Update

- Approximates the Hessian matrix using the Gauss–Newton method
 - Repeats until convergence
- well-regularized, generalized BRANN model

$$\alpha^{new} = \frac{\gamma}{2E_w(w^{new})}$$
$$\beta^{new} = \frac{n - \gamma}{2E_D(w^{new})}$$

This Bayesian framework allows BRANN to prevent overfitting automatically

Materials and Methods

Fatigue life prediction methodology

< Fatigue life prediction methodology >

- Fatigue test results are obtained from experimental data.
- Statistical analysis is performed to check the data quality
- If the logarithmic standard deviation $S_{\log} < 0.3S$, the data is considered reliable
- Input features such as joint type, maximum fatigue, load level, and overlap length are selected
- These inputs are fed into the BRANN model to predict fatigue life

Material Characterization

- USN 125B carbon/epoxy composite

-	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	ν	F_{1t}	F_{2t}	F_{1c}	F_{2c}	F_6
Unit	GPa	GPa	GPa	-	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa
USN-125 B	142	7.97	3.98	0.312	2419	48	1231	178	46

- SS400 Steel

-	E	σ_T	ν
Unit	GPa	MPa	-
SS400 Steel	206	313	0.29

- Type D adhesive

-	E	σ_T	ν
Unit	GPa	MPa	-
SS400 Steel	206	313	0.29

Tensile tests of bonded joint

< Tensile test result data >

	Overlap Length 30 mm	Overlap Length 40 mm	Overlap Length 50 mm
Failure Load (kN)	17.001	18.645	19.507
	17.445	18.289	19.582
	17.597	18.11	19.509
	17.727	18.710	19.236
	17.774	18.5545	19.206
	18.043	18.793	20.152
Average	17.598	18.517	19.532

< Failure loads for each overlap length >

- An increase in overlap length by 10 mm resulted in approximately a 5% increase in the failure load
- The increase in bonded area distributed the applied load and reduced internal stress

Tensile tests of hybrid joint

< Tensile test result data >

	Overlap Length 30mm	Overlap Length 40mm	Overlap Length 50mm
Failure load (kN)	13.321	17.856	18.751
	13.326	17.891	18.728
	13.439	18.833	18.315
	13.349	18.471	18.988
	14.152	18.2	18.125
	14.241	18.149	17.619
Average	13.638	18.233	18.421

< Failure loads for each overlap length >

- Two stages of failure behavior were observed: the first stage involved deformation and failure of the adhesive, and in the second stage, the load was transferred to the bolt, resulting in the second peak
- Performance varied depending on the effectiveness of load sharing
- An increase in overlap length by 10 mm resulted in increase in the failure load

Fatigue tests bonded joint

< The fatigue life data of the bonded single lap joints >

Overlap length 30mm			Overlap length 40mm			Overlap length 50mm		
Maximum fatigue load (kN)	Load level	Fatigue life (Cycle)	Maximum fatigue load (kN)	Load level	Fatigue Life (Cycle)	Maximum fatigue load (kN)	Load level	Fatigue Life (Cycle)
11.5043	0.65	7991	12.0354	0.65	45078	12.6962	0.65	162929
		12293			47200			109119
		13498			48793			130703
		13968			51569			100160
		15806			48972			125474
		18919			50148			147867
10.6194	0.6	17341	11.1096	0.6	79394	11.7196	0.6	361460
		18780			119575			293621
		19783			107701			276143
		23344			120143			245876
		25825			89724			224174
		29546			98271			214876
10.0884	0.57	49587	10.5541	0.57	193951	11.1332	0.57	335947
		51487			150167			477797
		52425			186606			607073
		57945			159846			524792
		62438			182546			340202
		65090			175483			425071

< F-N curves of the bonded single lap joints >

- All specimens had a failure at the joint with the adhesive
- Increasing the overlap length by 10 mm increased the joint's fatigue life by about 5 times

Fatigue tests hybrid joint

Slip (Adhesive failure)

< The fatigue life data of the hybrid joint >

Overlap length 30mm			Overlap length 40mm			Overlap length 50mm		
Maximum fatigue load (kN)	Load level	Fatigue life (Cycle)	Maximum fatigue load (kN)	Load level	Fatigue Life (Cycle)	Maximum fatigue load (kN)	Load level	Fatigue Life (Cycle)
11.5043	0.65	7991	12.0354	0.65	45078	12.6962	0.65	162929
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< F-N curves of the hybrid joint >

- The failure point was defined as the moment when the adhesive was completely failed
- As the overlap length increased from 30 mm to 40 mm, the fatigue life increased approximately 18 times, and as the overlap length increased from 40 mm to 50 mm, the fatigue life increased approximately 7 times

<Neural Network Learning Performance>

- Both training and test errors show a decreasing trend
- Minimum test MSE achieved at Epoch 4 (0.00399)
- Stable learning without signs of overfitting

<Training>

<Test>

<All>

- Strong linear correlation observed between predicted and target values
- R-values: Training = 1.00000, Validation = 0.99981, All = 0.99383
- These results confirm excellent model performance and generalization ability

Training Convergence

- Gradient decreased steadily, indicating smooth convergence of the training process
- Mu (damping factor) increased, showing that the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm approached convergence
- Gamma (Effective Parameters) stabilized around 20, suggesting efficient model complexity
- Sum of Squared Weights (ssX) remained bounded, preventing overfitting
- Validation Failures stayed at zero, confirming no degradation in generalization

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<Experimental and predicted fatigue life of bonded joints>

- A neural network was trained using hybrid joint fatigue data for 30, 40, and 50mm overlaps.
- The model predicted F–N curves for unseen lengths: 25, 35, 45, and 55 mm
- Experimental validation at 35 mm and 45 mm confirmed high prediction accuracy
- The model demonstrates strong generalization for fatigue life prediction

<Experimental and predicted fatigue life of hybrid joints>

- F-N (Force–Cycle) curves were predicted using a neural network trained on 30, 40, and 50mm overlap data.
- Predictions were extended to new overlap lengths: 25, 35, 45, and 55 mm
- The 35 mm prediction was experimentally validated, showing strong agreement
- The model demonstrates strong generalization for various hybrid joint configurations

Expected Effects of Research

Original fatigue life forecasting method

Inaccurate when applied to dissimilar material joints
Prone to overfitting and poor generalization

Fatigue life prediction method in this study

<Experimental setup for fatigue tests of single lap joints and hybrid joints>

- Accurate fatigue life prediction for bonded and hybrid joints with varying overlap lengths
 - Effective overfitting mitigation via Bayesian regularization

Summary & Future Works

Summary

- Proposed a fatigue life prediction method for dissimilar material joints using a neural network
- Constructed experimental F-N data for bonded and hybrid joints with varying overlap lengths
- Trained a Bayesian Regularized Neural Network (BRANN) using fatigue data from 30, 40, and 50mm overlaps
- Predicted fatigue life for unseen overlap lengths (25, 35, 45, 55 mm) using the trained model
- Prediction accuracy was validated at 35 mm and 45 mm overlaps, showing good agreement with experiments

Future Works

- Expand training dataset to cover more diverse joint configurations and loading conditions
- Apply model to multi-axial fatigue cases and real structural joint geometries

Q & A

Thank you
